

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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*Elektron nashr. 1445 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'lqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozorida emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qardorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	

Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukrullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruza Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	
Agroklasterning tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati	219
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich	
"Yashil" Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda turizmga investitsiyalarning roli.....	224
Azimov Olimjon Orifovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida aholini ro'yxatga olish jarayonlarini samarali tashkil etish	236
Annazarova Barno Rustamovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida sug'oriladigan yerlar unumdorligini oshirishni iqtisodiy rag'batlantirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	242
Isaxanov Muslimjon Ma'rifjon o'g'li	

Logistika va uning sanoat mahsulot ishlab chiqarish tannarxiga ta'sirini kamaytirish	246
Zokirjonov Asadbek Otabek o'g'li	
Sug'urta kampaniyalari moliyaviy risklarini baholash	249
Baymuratova Gulirayxon Tursunbaevna	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyati tushunchasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	255
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Qishloqlarning resurs salohiyati iqtisodiy kategoriya va iqtisodiyotning agrar sektorini rivojlantirishning zaruriy sharti sifatida	260
Tursunpo'latov Farxodjon Xoshimjon o'g'li	
Kommunal xizmatlarni rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish	265
Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi	
Analysis of factors affecting the sustainable development of transport networks in Khorezm	269
Karimboev Dilshod Davronbek o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini tashkiliy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	274
Lutfullo Xalimovich Qadirov	
Использование социальных сетей как инструмента маркетинга для фермеров	278
Назарова Гулрух Умаржонова	
O'zbekiston transport-logistika tizimida logistika samaradorligi indeksi (LPI) va uning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatidagi ahamiyati	283
Ismoilov Narimonjon No'monjon o'g'li	
Davlat maqsadli dasturlarini imtiyozli kreditlash tizimining mamlakat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni	287
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda potensial YaIM.ning ekonometrik tahlili	293
Djabbarov Raximjon Abdullaevich	
Tibbiyot muassasalarini kafolatlangan tibbiy xizmatlar paketi asosida moliyalashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish masalalari	298
Muxammadiev Ramz Zoirjon o'g'li	
Стратегии развития медицинских организаций в Узбекистане	313
Исломбек Умиров	
Kambag'allikka qarshi kurashning falsafiy va ijtimoiy asoslari: Tarixiy tahlil	321
Iloxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o'g'li	
Innovatsion loyihalar va startaplarni moliyalashtirishda venchur fondlarining ahamiyati	329
Atamuradov Sherzod Akramovich	
Reforms in higher education institutions of the republic of uzbekistan	334
Gafurov Anvar Bazarbayevich	
Namangan viloyati qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining faoliyati samaradorligini ta'minlash holati va tahlili	343
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o'g'li	
Increasing the innovation potential of construction materials industry enterprises	350
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
Jahon savdo tashkiloti doirasida to'qimachilik mahsulotlarining xalqaro savdosi	356
Nurboev Jaloliddin Mamadiyevich, Abduvohidov Behzod	
Farg'ona vodiysida turizm xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlili	361
Mamatqulov Zarifbek Sharifjonovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari	366
Ko'chqarov Fayzullo Abdujabborovich	
Tarkibiy o'zgarishlar sharoitlarida xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda investitsiyalarni faollashtirish	376
M.J.Nabiyeva	
O'zbekistonda aholi omonatlari va ularni kafolatlash tizimi	382
Xakimov Zohid Norbo'tayevich	

Взаимодействие образования и бизнеса с элементами дуального образования	389
Баходурова Сулхия Азизхожаевна, Акрамова Зарринадон Башировна, Ли Марина Рудольфовна, Ромашкин Роман Анатольевич, Мухтарова Доната Равшанбековна	
О'zbekistonda yashirin iqtisodiyot darajasini qisqartirishda samarali yondoshuv.....	396
Bobojonov Azimjon Akmal o'g'li	
To'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyalarini takomillashtirish zaruriyati.....	403
Sarimsaqov Doniyor Xomidovich	
Xorazm viloyatida hududiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish darajasini baholash	409
Madraximov Kaxramon Egamberganovich	
O'zbekistonda aholini uy-joy bilan ta'minlashdagi murakkabliklar va ularning yechimlari.....	414
Xannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
Elektron hukumatdan smart hukumatga	419
Abidov Abdjabbar Abduxamidovich	
Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznesni rivojlanishi va samaradorligining nazariy-uslubiy asoslar	426
Axatova Shahnoza	
O'zbekistonda banklar faoliyatini tartibga solishning zamonaviy mexanizmlari	432
Abdullaev Suyun Artikovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya va hududlarning inklyuziv iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	436
Zokirova Bahora Zokir qizi	
Market research strategies in the global tech industry: a comparative study of apple, samsung, and huawei	440
Abbos Ruzmamatov	
Strategic analysis of innovation development in manufacturing enterprises: approaches, challenges, and future perspectives.....	444
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda moliyalashtirish texnologiyasi	452
Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich	
Boshqarish jarayonlarini samaradorligini oshirish orqali iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash	459
Xo'jamurodov Asqarjon Jalolovich, Usmonov Suxrob Zayniddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni: amalga oshirish imkoniyatlari va kelajak istiqbollari	469
Kurbanov Farrux Uktamovich	
Kichik biznes uchun investitsion muhit jozibadorligining ko'rsatkichlari tahlili	469
Jurayev Elyorbek Sobirjon o'g'li, Nabiyeva Muhabbat Djabirxonovna	
Fiskal va monetar siyosatni muvofiqlashtirishda inflyatsiya ko'rsatkichining ekonometrik tahlili	475
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Bandlikni ta'minlashning moliyaviy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	479
Karimjonov Muhammadrasul To'liqinjon o'g'li	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
Аутсорсинг и рост сферы услуг: воздействие на занятость (практика США)	494
Назаров Зиёвуддин Шарофиддинович	
Restoran xizmatlari sohasi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda marketingning zamonaviy konsepsiyalarini qo'llash.....	501
Ibodov Kamoliddin Mamatqulovich	
The revenue manager in the hospitality industry	507
Kalandarova Gulnoza	

Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini joriy etilishi bo'yicha ayrim xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari	510
B.Turabov	
Barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlashning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	517
Baxtiyorova Dildora	
Elektr energiyasi samaradorligini yaxshilashga innovatsion va strategik yondashuvlar.....	521
Doliyev Shoxabbos Qulmurot o'g'li	
Don maxsulotlari sifat ko'rsatkichlariga sovuq konditsionerlash tizimini samaradorligini tahlil qilish	525
Yusupov Azamat Alijonovich, Akramova Gulhayo Abidovna	
O'zbekistonda tijorat banklarini rivojlantirish va transformatsiya qilish istiqbollari	532
Mutalova Mohira	
Optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks	537
Muydinov Muhammadsardor Abdukayum ugli	
Ochiq bank (open banking) faoliyatining xalqaro tajribasi va o'zbekistonda qo'llanilishi	541
Xoshimov Elmurod Abdusattorovich, Abduvahobov Shohruh Xolmo'min o'g'li	
Mikrosug'urtaning kichik biznes risklarini sug'urtalashning innovatsion mexanizmi sifatidagi ahamiyati.....	549
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
Agroklastarlarni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashning iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	553
Topildiev Soxibjon Raximjonovich, Nasirxodjayeva Dilafruz Sabitxanovna	
Econometric analysis and adjustment of agricultural production processes.....	563
Makhambetova Uringul	
The importance of investing investment in fixed capital.....	568
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Ruzimatov Sanjarbek Qosimjon ugli	
Kichik biznes iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda kasanachilik va mahalliy yetkazib beruvchilarni rivojlantirish	573
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari bozorining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	577
Zaidov Islom Ibragimjonovich	
Respublika iqtisodiyotining innovatsion salohiyati va undan foydalanish.....	583
Olchinboyev Otabek Abdusamad o'g'li	
Математическое моделирование забойки при использовании вв с экспоненциальным внешнем воздействием	587
Джураева Нодира Мурадullaевна	
Kichik biznes subyektlari faoliyatini moliyaviy ta'minoti masalalari.....	593
Aymurzaeva Gulnaz Puxarbaevna	
Logistika harajatlarini optimallashtirish shartlari.....	598
N.B. Shanazarova	
G'o'zaning yangi tizmalari tolasining sifat ko'rsatkichlari	603
X.A.Boltabaev, X.A.Mamadjonov	
Aholi turmush darajasi baholashda daromadlarning ahamiyati	607
Tursunov Farxod Baxodir o'g'li, Qambarov Bahriddin Panji o'g'li	
Xodimlar bilan hisob-kitoblar hisobining nazariy va normativ-huquqiy asoslari.....	618
Ametova Nasiba Danilovna	
Nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar boshqaruvida zaifliklar	622
Odilbekova Dilnoza Murataliyevna	
Respublika iqtisodiyotida oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlanish tendensiyalari	626
Baxritdinov Sherzodbek Bahodirovich	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning xorijiy ilg'or davlatlar tajribasi.....	631
Qaxxorov Shoxruxbek Shavkatjon o'g'li	
Порядок аудита лизинговых операций.....	636
Турсунов Улугбек Сативолдиевич	

Fond bozorida aksiyalar muomalasi tahlili.....	641
Quvondiqov Muhammad Quvondiqovich	
Низкоуглеродное развитие: ключевой фактор устойчивого развития в узбекистане и мировом контексте.....	646
Исламов Шохзод Шухрат ўғли	
Устойчивое управление ресурсами: роль государственного управления, квоты на природные ресурсы и производительности энергии.....	653
Ибрагимов Захид Тахирович	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda sanoat korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash va rivojlantirish usullari.....	661
Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich	
Food security problems.....	667
Shukurov Tohirjon Izzatullo o'g'li	
Waste management in the dairy industry.....	669
Shukurov Izzatullo Khikmatullaevich	
Sanoat korxonalariga kiritilgan investitsiyalar samaradorligining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	675
Feruz Hojiqulova Dona qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini eksport salohiyatini oshirishda vujudga kelayotgan muammolar va ularning yechimlari.....	683
Yuldasheva Dildora Kamiljan qizi	
O'zbekistonda budjet tashkilotlarida moliyaviy nazoratini olib borishning ustuvor yo'llari.....	687
Alxanova Feruz Faxritdinovna	
O'zbekistonda davlat xaridlari tizimini takomillashtirish.....	691
Shermatov G'ofurjon G'ulamovich, Mamasoliev Abrorbek Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Kichik tadbirkorlik tarkibiy tuzilmasi takomillashuvida tarmoq bo'yicha ixtisoslashuv jarayonlarining ahamiyati va ularning rivojlanganlik darajasiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar.....	696
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli platformalar orqali yashil mahsulotlar va xizmatlarni rivojlantirish.....	709
Nurmetova Muyassar Jumanazarovna	
Development and practical application of financial security indicators at the regional level: The case of Uzbekistan.....	715
Elmurodov Shohzod Shavkatovich	
Boshqaruv psixologiyasining terminologik tahlili va semantik xususiyatlari.....	720
Norboyeva Dilafruza Jumaqulovna	
Mintaqa ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga kiritilgan investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili.....	724
Tursunpulat Davronovich Maxmudov	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlar mahsulotlar eksportini motivatsiyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	730
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish huquqiy kafolatlari.....	735
Usmonov Shavkatjon Shukurovich	
Nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyatini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashning amaliy jihatlari.....	744
Muslitdinov Nodir Xojievich	
Korxonalarda qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini joriy etish sharoitida strategik loyixa boshqaruvi.....	750
Orifali Samandarovich Tursunov, Xalilov Jaxangir Jalolovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro fond bozori holati tahlili.....	756
Shamsiev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarini innovasion faoliyatini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash yo'llari.....	764
Shaniyazova Zamira Oralbaevna	

Raqamli transformasiya jarayonlarining bank xizmatlari sifati va xavfsizligini oshirishga ta'siri.....	772
Qodirov Bekzod Xushnud o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari ipoteka xizmatini raqamlashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	776
Jabbarov Majidbek Erzodovich	
Fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyati samaradorligini statistik usullarda baholash.....	780
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
Sanoat korxonalarida moliyaviy barqarorlik, ularni hisoblash va oshirish yo'llari.....	784
Makhkamova Shakhruza Bahodir qizi	
O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan chora-tadbirlar.....	788
G'ofurjon Shermatov G'ulamovich, Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Tannarxni pasaytirishda ish vaqtdan samarali foydalanish va mehnat sig'imi tahlili.....	794
Xamidova S.Ya.	
Umumta'lim muassasalari xarajatlarini moliyalashtirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	799
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'idagi tarkibiy-tuzilmaviy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....	803
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
Measures for the development of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan.....	813
Khallieva Nargiza Rozikovna	
Turizmda raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash bo'yicha jaxon tajribasi.....	820
Jalolov Otabek Oybek o'g'li	
Формирование страхового бизнеса как стратегического сектора экономики.....	826
Тулаев Дилшод Юсуфович	
Особенности использования инструментов монетарной политики в зарубежных странах.....	831
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
Некоторые аспекты технологического развития в современной экономике.....	839
Ахмедов К.	
Формирование конкурентоспособных профессионалов для рынка.....	842
Ишимбаев Рафаэль Наильевич	
Влияние инвестиций на оценку эффективности использования интеллектуального капитала.....	848
Муртазаев Ардашер Зафар угли	
Navoiy viloyatida kichik biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirish holatini statistik bashorat qilish.....	853
Xushvaqova Durdona Islom qizi	
Foreign trade liberalization and its impact on a country's economic growth (in the case of countries).....	860
Sirajiddinov Nishanbay, Norkobilov Akobir	
Samarqand viloyati xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	871
Umirov Islombek Furkatovich, Ozodxonov Islombek Zarifxon o'g'li, Turaqulov Ulug'bek Shovkat o'g'li	
O'zbekistonning jahon savdo tashkilotiga qoshilishi natijasida xom ashyolar importining yengillashishi va mahsulotga ketadigan xarajatlarning kamayishi masalalari.....	880
Z.K. Xashimova	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarining samaradorligini ekonometrik modellashtirish.....	885
Musurmonova Mahbuba Omonovna	
Yuqori malakali kadrlar tayyorlash samaradorligi iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili.....	892
Zaripova Mukaddas Djumayozovna	
Xususiy kredit – kreditning zamonaviy turi sifatida.....	902
Sharbat Abdullaeva, Abdullaev Sardor Atxam o'g'li	

Jahon iqtisodiyotida yuzaga kelgan megatrendlarning o'zbekistonning tashqi savdo munosabatlariga ta'siri.....	907
Yangibaeva Dilafuz Polat qizi	
Issues of reflection of financial results in reports and improvement of audit	912
Muhammedova Dilfuza Anvarovna, Shukurov Farrux Shuxrat o'g'li	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlar mahsulotlar eksportini motivatsiyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	918
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Mamlakatimizda uy xo'jaliklari iqtisodiy faolligini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	918
Abdullayev S.A.	
Etnografik turizm samaradorligini oshirishda xorij tajribasini qo'llash	922
Xakimov Dilyor Zafarovich	
Davlat muassasalarida inson resurslaridan foydalanish samaradorligining statistik tadqiqi	930
Xusanova Muxsina Kasimovna	
Raqamli marketing va barqaror strategiyalar orqali mintaqaviy investitsiyaviy jozibadorlikni oshirish: AHP asosidagi tahlil.....	937
Xolmurotova Diyoraxon Ibragimovna	
Sanoat korxonalarida iqtisodiy salohiyatni rivojlantirishda qo'laniladigan strategiyalar	943
Turaboyev Ibroxim Ismoil o'g'li	
Innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishi.....	948
Maxmudov Abrorxon Axmadxonovich	
Issues of strategic planning in industrial enterprises.....	952
Ibragimov Isroil Usmanovich	
Sanoat korxonalarida tejamkor texnologiyalarni joriy qilishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	958
Xakimov Umarxon Rustamjon o'g'li	
Цифровая экономика: концептуальные основы и ее влияние на трансформация рынка труда.....	962
Магруппов Азиз Юлдашевич	
Taraqqiyot strategiyasi va ma'muriy islohotlarning keyingi bosqichlari.....	971
Abdulla Abdulkadirov	
Экономический эффект от внедрения международных образовательных стандартов в узбекистане	977
Олимова Бахора Шухратовна	
Ijtimoiy xizmatlar sohasini rivojlanish tendentsiyalari va davlat-xususiy sherikligini samarali shakllantirish mexanizmlari	981
Y.M.Xalikov	
Qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarilishida kimyo sanoatining o'rni	988
Usmanov Baxtiyor Xusanboyevich	
Hududiy sanoatni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati va uning salohiyatini belgilovchi omillar	994
Choriyev Tolib A'zamovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida banklar faoliyatini innovatsion rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	999
Qosimova Mohigul Abduhamidovna	
Tasvirlarni intellektuallashtirishda filtrlash jarayoni va baholash algoritmlari	1004
Norboyeva Nafisa	
Model of application of the integrated report on the organisation's human capital in management accounting	1009
Ochilov Olmos Ikrom ugli	
To'qimachilik tarmog'ini iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini modellashtirish va prognozlash yo'nalishlari.....	1018
Madraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
O'zbekiston-Yaponiya yashil iqtisodiyoti sharoitida turizm soxasi bo'yicha xamkorlik.....	1023
Dadaxanov Shuxrat Abdumalikovich	

Изменение климата и зеленая экономика: стратегии и меры в узбекистане.....	1027
Хусайнов Равшан Рахимович, Ибрагимова Камола Саидбариевна	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining barqaror rivojlanishi: investisiya faoliyatining ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	1033
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Rahmonova Durdona Hasan qizi	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini hisobga olish.....	1040
Xamidova S.Y.	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan aholiga ko'rsatiladigan xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	1040
Rajabov S.	
Проблемы микрокредитования малого бизнеса и кредитная поддержка частного предпринимательства в республике Узбекистан.....	1045
Сохибов Ж.Т.	
Эмоциональный интеллект и его влияние на эффективность принятия решений лидерами.....	1049
Юлдашева Камола Касымджановна	
Sanoat korxonalarini investitsion jozibadorligini aniqlash usullari.....	1055
Anafiyayev Abdurashid Mamasidiqovich	
Tijorat banklari investitsion jozibadorligini oshirishda dividend siyosatining o'rni.....	1060
Azimjon Abdiraxmonov	
Mahalliy soliqlar va ularning iqtisodiy ahamiyati, soliq bazasini kengaytirish va soliq madaniyatini oshirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1065
Ravshanov Xurshid Akramovich	
Banklar samaradorligi va kapital yetarliqlik ko'rsatkichi riski o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik tahlili.....	1069
Xoldorov Sardor Umarovich	
Управление процессом снижения трансакционных издержек в условиях экологизации экономики.....	1075
Ходжаева Нодирахон Абдурашидовна	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bozorida yashil marketing strategiyasini qo'llash.....	1078
Po'latova Shahnoza Abdirashitovna	
Agriculture cooperative models.....	1082
Qo'ldosheva Gulnozaxon Shukurjon qizi	
Iqtisodiy mutanosiblik va uni ta'minlashning ayrim nazariy masalalari.....	1086
Murtazayev Isabek Bazarbayevich	
Biohududlar yashil maqsadlarga erishish yo'lidagi ahamiyati.....	1094
Galimova Firuza, Dexkanova Nilufar	
MDH mintaqasida transport sohasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirishda EOII transport integratsiyasining tashqi omillari va xavflari.....	1099
Xo'jayev Fazliddin Elmurodovich	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes subyektlarining eksport faoliyatini moliyalashtirish mexanizmlari.....	1103
Abdumo'minov Axrorjon Axatjonovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda transport tizimini o'rni.....	1107
Abduraxmanova Muqaddas Toxtasinovna	
Korxonada marketingning strategik ahamiyati.....	1113
Egamberdiyev Muzaffar	
Jismoniy shaxslarni kreditlash jarayonlarini takomillashtirish.....	1116
Jurayeva Sevara Zakirovna	
Assessing the effects of GDP expansion on environmental degradation in uzbekistan.....	1122
Muhammad Eid Balbaa	
Innovation jarayonlarni boshqarish samaradorligini baholashning uslubiy jihatlari.....	1132
To'g'onov Ibrohimxo'ja Otaxo'ja o'gli	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari sohasida nomoddiy aktivlar hisobi va uni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	1137
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillayevich	

The impact of agricultural production on food security in Uzbekistan in the coming years.....	1142
Saydullayev Abbos, Khudoyberdiyev Diyorbek	
Mintaqaviy agrosanoat majmuasida klasterlashning holatini o'rganish va baholashga ilmiy-uslubiy yondashuvlarni tizimlashtirish.....	1148
A.Ch.Boboyev, M.O.Shamsiyeva	
Hududiy barqaror rivojlanishning nazariy asoslari.....	1153
Nazarov Nazirjon Narzilloevich, Umarov Oqil Omiljonovich	
“Asosiy kapitalning iqtisodiy mohiyati, uni tashkil etish va moliyalashtirishning nazariy asoslari”	1158
Zoxidov Tohirjon Mirzfar o'g'li	
Асимптотические свойства момента останова в последовательном оценивании	1162
Турсунов Гафур Таирович	
Qimmatli qog'orlar bozorini raqamlashtirishda tijorat banklarining o'rni.....	1169
Abdukayumov Abduvaxid Abduvasikovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan to'lovga layoqatlilikni baholashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1175
Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li	
Цифровые технологии как драйверы улучшения финансовой оценки предприятий.....	1181
Юсупов Файзулла Якубович	
Qishloq xo'jaligi samaradorligini oshirishda logistikaning zaruriyati va ilmiy asoslari.....	1190
Abdirashidov Temurbek Abdirashid o'g'li	
To'qimachilik sanoati tarmog'ida innovatsion klasterlarni boshqarish mexanizmi	1194
Muminova Elnorakhon Abduakrimovna	
Milliy iqtisodiyotni innovatsion rivojlantirish asosida barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni taminlash	1201
Fayzieva Nilufar Shuxrat qizi	
Пути совершенствования практики управления государственным внешним долгом.....	1206
Бобаккулов Тулкин Ибодуллаевич, Расулова Саида Талатовна	
Moliyaviy pufak xavfi indeksi va uni tijorat banklari faoliyatiga ta'sirini baholash	1210
Botirov Islombek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Ta'lim oluvchilar kognitiv faolligini rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi o'ziga xos jihatlari.....	1215
Panjiyev Maqsud Aliqulovich	
O'zbekistonda tarmoqlararo klasterlar samaradorligini baholashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1219
Sharipova Zulayho Abdirimovna	
Пути развития фондового рынка на основе цифровых технологий.....	1124
Шукурова Луиза Баратовна, Эшдавлатов Боймурод Соатович	
Riskka asoslangan ichki audit o'tkazishning iqtisodiy mazmuni hamda tashkil etish muammolari	1228
Asfandiyorova Shakina Rustam qizi	
Anoat klasterlarining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi	1231
Saidaxmedov Nemat Hamidovich	
Servis sohasida kichik korxonalar faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish va ularning mezonlari	1237
Umirov Islombek Furkatovich, Xurramov Shohjahon Abror o'g'li, Muhammadiyev Humoyun Omon o'g'li, Nishonov Ayubxon Isroiljon o'g'li	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning agrar soha rivojiga ta'siri: xorij tajribasi.....	1244
Mambetnazarov Bakhit Bisenbayevich	
Sog'lomlashtirish turizmi faoliyatining boshqaruv samaradorligi: boshqaruv strategiyasi va uning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari	1248
G'ofurov Azizbek Umarjonovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida yuk avtomobillari transport xizmatlari ko'rsatish tizimini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslari.....	1253
Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirish – yuqori iqtisodiy o'sish omili sifatida	1257
Muminova Elnorakhon Abduakrimovna, Jo'rayev Asadbek Anvarjon o'g'li	

Korxonalar daromadiga ta'sir qiluvchi risklarni boshqarish asoslarini takomillashtirish	1263
Sa'dullayev Oybek Turdiali o'g'li	
Aholini ish bilan ta'minlashning ijtimoiy – iqtisodiy va huquqiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	1268
Zufarova Gulmira Abduxalilovna	
Strategik menejment yondashuvlari asosida oliy ta'lim tizimi boshqaruvining xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi.....	1272
Avezova Shaxnoza Maxmudjonovna, Po'lotov Shoxrux Shavkatovich	
Uzoq muddatli aktivlarga amortizatsiya hisoblash usullari.....	1278
Xamdamova Ra'no Bahodir qizi, Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
Iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiya qilish va uning afzalliklari.....	1284
Mirzarayimova Feruza Zokirjon qizi, Levakov Izzatulla Nematillayevich	
Tijorat banklarining aktiv operatsiyalari risklarini ekonometrik baholash.....	1288
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Mechanisms of production management within the framework of the strategy of Uzbekistan	1293
Ziyayeva M.M.	
Sustainable development priorities and ensuring environmental sustainability: prospects for Uzbekistan.....	1297
Seitova Leila Pulatovna	
Davlat dasturlarining ijrosi samaradorligini oshirishda samaradorlik auditining rolini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1303
Behzod Shamsiddinovich Mirzoev	
Mintaqa xalq hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish orqali aholi bandligini ta'minlashning tahlili.....	1310
Norqobilova Feruza Abduhomidovna	
Qoraqalpog'iston respublikasida turistik xizmatlar bozorini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	1314
Kusekeev Bayram Kallibekovich	
Korxonalarda kadrlar siyosati va mehnatni tashkil etish.....	1319
Obidxonov Javoxirxon Avaxonovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi sharoitida kunjut yetishtirishni ekonometrik modellashtirish va iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1324
Otemisov Sharapat Jangabayevich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiy xavfsizligini taminlashda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligining o'rni (O'zbekiston Respublikasi misolida).....	1332
Hamidov Mahmudjon Abdug'affor o'g'li, Mamasoliyeva Maktuba Axmadullayevna	
Pul aylanmasi mexanizmini amaliy asoslarini takomillashtirish.....	1338
Gadoyev So'hrob Jumakulovich	
Inson kapitali iqtisodiy kategoriya sifatida mohiyatini va unda ta'limni o'rni.....	1345
Abduraxmanov Kamoliddin Batirovich	
The role of introduction of the concept "economic production" in industrial enterprises in the development of small business.....	1351
Kamilova Anora Nasirovna	
O'zbekistonda vakolatli iqtisodiy operatorlar faoliyatini tartibga solish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	1355
Yo'ldoshev Jasurbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida kichik sanoat zonalari faoliyati samaradorligini baholashning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslari.....	1360
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillaevich	
Qoraqalpog'iston respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirishning zamonaviy imkoniyatlari	1364
Isakov Janabay Yakirbaevich	
Investitsion salohiyat tushunchasi va uni boshqarishning zarurligi	1375
To'raev Jasurali To'raevich	
Samarali boshqaruv strategiyalarini shakllantirishda energiya sarfini optimallashtirish usullari	1379
Xamdamova Gavxar Absamatovna	

Banklarga zamonaviy xizmat turlarini joriy etishda infratuzilmaning roli	1385
Umarova Malika Baxtiyarovna	
Turistik korxonalar raqobatbardoshligi mohiyati	1391
Mahamadova Muslimaxon Muzaffar qizi	
Tijorat banklarida innovation faoliyatni rivojlantirish strategiyasining asosiy yo'nalishlari	1394
Rahmanov Zafar Yashinovich	
O'zbekiston yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish yo'lida: barqaror rivojlanish va energiya samaradorligi.....	1398
Nabiyev Olimjon Abdusalomovich	
Ishsizlikda gender tengsizligini aniqlash metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	1403
Oxunova Oygul Usmonjon qizi	
“O'zbekneftgaz” AJ korxonalariga kiritilayotgan investisiyalarning iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlili	1409
Yuldoshev Sobir Fayzullaevich	
Сотрудничество таможи с промышленностью: новый взгляд на обеспечение глобальной безопасности и экономической стабильности	1414
Муратова Шохиста Ниматуллаевна	
Agrar sohada kadrlar salohiyatining ishlab chiqarish samaradorligiga ta'siri	1420
Boltayev Nazarbek Narzullayevich	
Влияние туризма на рост экспорта текстильной продукции	1426
Сулейманова Шоира Алавхановна	
The revenue manager in the hospitality industry	1441
Kalandarova Gulnoza	

satisfaction and loyalty, even when dynamic pricing is applied. This study provided insights into how revenue managers can balance profitability with customer trust.

McGuire and Kimes (2006) analyzed the growing influence of technology on revenue management, particularly the adoption of revenue management systems (RMS). Their findings highlighted that sophisticated algorithms and data integration capabilities allow revenue managers to forecast demand more accurately and implement targeted pricing strategies.

Ivanov and Zhechev (2012) provided a comprehensive overview of revenue management tools and techniques specific to the hospitality industry. Their research categorized these tools into forecasting, pricing, and inventory control, emphasizing that successful implementation depends on the skills and expertise of revenue managers.

Guillet and Mohammed (2015) discussed the role of digital marketing in supporting revenue management. They noted that effective online distribution channels and personalized marketing campaigns are essential for driving demand and optimizing revenue streams.

The reviewed studies collectively demonstrate that revenue management in the hospitality industry is a multifaceted discipline requiring a balance between technology, customer relations, and market analysis. The integration of advanced technologies such as RMS and dynamic pricing models provides a competitive edge, while maintaining customer trust and transparency ensures long-term success. These insights highlight the evolving role of revenue managers as both strategists and data-driven decision-makers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involved collecting primary data through structured interviews and surveys with revenue managers to understand their strategies and practices. Secondary data was obtained from industry reports and academic sources for broader context. Data analysis combined thematic coding for qualitative insights and statistical tools for quantitative correlations, ensuring comprehensive and reliable results.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The information gathered on how your customers think and perceive value will ultimately be utilized to match your supply to their demand. This will help you determine when it is best to hold onto a room until you can achieve a higher price and how to recognize a drop in demand, signaling the time for discounted rates. The key to an effective revenue management strategy lies in the ability to make accurate forecasts of your potential consumers' spending habits and the demand for your product. These forecasts may include past and current bookings, weather conditions, tourism statistics, and other industry data. With this information, you can make informed adjustments when necessary.

The four pillars of revenue management, often referred to as the 4Ps, are Pricing, Positioning, Pace, and Performance. Each element plays a crucial role in forming a comprehensive revenue strategy and will be discussed in detail in a 4-part blog series.

A hotel's revenue manager holds the responsibility of setting prices that maximize the hotel's profitability and align with its strategic objectives. While this task might initially seem straightforward, it requires a combination of analytical skills, market research, critical thinking, and even a touch of intuition to make effective pricing decisions. Excellent revenue managers must also balance the mix of group and transient business, which often involves collaboration and negotiation between marketing and sales teams.

Revenue management also involves promoting the most suitable accommodations to the appropriate clients at the right prices and at optimal times, utilizing targeted distribution channels. This approach provides a cost-effective solution while ensuring customer satisfaction.

To develop the most effective strategies, revenue managers often rely on analytics and various data points. Common factors that are typically analyzed include:

- Predicting demand.
- Identifying behavioral trends, such as periods with the highest booking rates.
- Understanding consumer spending habits.
- Creating dynamic pricing packages.
- Analyzing competitors' pricing strategies through business intelligence.

Understanding these concepts enables management to make informed decisions and ensures that revenue is generated and utilized efficiently. In essence, revenue management depends on addressing the "who, what, where, why, and how" of the hotel industry.

The hospitality industry is a vast and dynamic sector that encompasses a wide range of services, primarily focused on accommodating guests and ensuring their satisfaction. This includes various segments such as

hotels, resorts, restaurants, travel, event planning, and other tourism-related services. The industry's primary goal is to deliver comfortable, enjoyable, and high-quality experiences for guests while maintaining financial sustainability and fostering growth for businesses within it.

The hospitality industry is a significant contributor to global economies, generating billions of dollars annually and providing millions of jobs worldwide. These jobs span beyond hotels and restaurants, extending to supporting industries such as construction, real estate, transportation, and manufacturing.

The industry is one of the largest employers globally, offering diverse opportunities ranging from entry-level positions in housekeeping to senior roles in hotel management. Careers in hospitality can encompass various fields, including customer service, event planning, culinary arts, travel, and tourism.

Hospitality plays a vital role in fostering cross-cultural exchange by bringing people from different parts of the world together. It enables travelers to experience new destinations, local cuisines, and unique customs, thereby promoting understanding and appreciation of different cultures.

As technology evolves, the hospitality industry has integrated numerous innovations to enhance guest experiences and streamline operations. Mobile apps for booking and check-in, artificial intelligence (AI) for personalization, and automation systems for resource management have become essential tools in modern hospitality management.

In Uzbekistan, the state program for implementing the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60, outlines measures to support the tourism sector. Specifically, from April 1, 2024, to April 1, 2026, business entities providing hotel services will receive subsidies allocated from the Tourism Support Fund. For each quarter, subsidies are available for hotels that meet accessibility standards, such as equipping at least three rooms with facilities for wheelchair users and installing displays and sound devices for enhanced accessibility. The subsidy amounts are as follows:

- For star hotels: 2 million soums per specially equipped room.
- For non-star hotels: 1 million soums per specially equipped room.

Revenue management is an essential practice for achieving long-term success in the hospitality sector. By analyzing historical and current data, hoteliers can develop dynamic strategies aligned with the needs of their hotels and customers.

Artificial intelligence and automated processes have transformed the sector by simplifying operations, creating memorable guest experiences, and increasing profitability. These technologies also enable innovation by highlighting services that hotels could benefit from, which may not have been previously considered.

Revenue management contributes to improving hotel efficiency, reducing costs, enhancing demand forecasting, determining optimal staffing levels, and maintaining a competitive edge. It is a core component of hotel management, helping businesses achieve profitability while delivering the quality service and amenities that customers expect.

The hospitality industry is a cornerstone of the global economy, offering diverse services designed to enhance guest experiences while driving business profitability. From revenue management and customer satisfaction to technological adoption and sustainability, the industry encompasses numerous aspects critical to success. As the sector evolves, staying attuned to trends, data analysis, and consumer behavior is imperative for professionals aiming to remain competitive in this fast-paced market.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The research findings underscore the critical role of revenue managers in optimizing financial outcomes in the hospitality industry. By employing a combination of advanced pricing strategies, demand forecasting, and technology integration, revenue managers significantly contribute to maximizing revenue while maintaining customer satisfaction. The use of structured interviews and surveys provided direct insights into the practical challenges and innovative solutions adopted by revenue managers, highlighting their adaptability in a competitive environment.

The integration of secondary data further enriched the research, offering a broader understanding of global trends and best practices in revenue management. Qualitative analysis revealed key themes such as the importance of transparent pricing policies and the growing reliance on data-driven decision-making tools. Quantitative analysis demonstrated clear correlations between strategic pricing decisions, occupancy rates, and profitability, emphasizing the measurable impact of effective revenue management.

In conclusion, the study illustrates that revenue managers are not only key strategists but also pivotal contributors to the financial success of hospitality businesses. Their ability to balance technology, market trends, and customer expectations ensures sustainable growth and competitiveness in an ever-evolving industry. Future research could explore emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, to further enhance revenue management practices.

List of used literature

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PQ-20 dated 12.01.2024
2. John Wiley & Sons, Inc, REVENUE MANAGEMENT HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY, 2011, Published simultaneously in Canada
3. Enz, C. A., & Siguaw, J. A. (2000). Best Practices in Hotel Operations. Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly, 41(5), 50–62.
4. Chiang, W. C., Chen, J. C. H., & Xu, X. (2007). An Overview of Research on Revenue Management: Current Issues and Future Research. International Journal of Revenue Management, 1(1), 97–128.
5. Kimes, S. E., & Wirtz, J. (2003). Has Revenue Management Become Acceptable? Findings from an International Study on the Perceived Fairness of Rate Fences. Journal of Service Research, 6(2), 125–135.
6. McGuire, K., & Kimes, S. E. (2006). The Perceived Fairness of Revenue Management Pricing in the U.S. Golf Industry. International Journal of Hospitality Management, 25(1), 106–123.
7. Ivanov, S., & Zhechev, V. (2012). Hotel Revenue Management – A Critical Literature Review. Tourism Management Studies, 8(2), 5–15.
8. Guillet, B. D., & Mohammed, I. (2015). Revenue Management and Digital Marketing in the Hotel Industry. Tourism Management Perspectives, 15, 87–90.
9. <https://hospitalityinsights.ehl.edu/what-revenue-management#:~:text=Q%20%3A%20What%20is%20Revenue%20Management,to%20pricing%20and%20distribution%20strategies>.
10. <https://www.mews.com/en/blog/hotel-revenue-manager>
11. <https://www.mews.com/en/blog/what-is-revenue-management> <https://www.revfine.com/hotel-industry/>

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

